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STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF ACTIVE AND REACTIVE POWER LOSSES IN DISTRIBUTION ELECTRIC NETWORKS

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Annotation. In this paper, on the basis of statistical analysis, the expediency of reduce reactive energy losses under operating conditions is shown to improve the efficiency of the distribution electrical networks. An analysis of the circuit-mode situation and a structural analysis of reactive energy losses were made on the example of a distribution electrical network with a voltage of 6 kV. The centers of increased losses of active and reactive energy are revealed. The effect of reduce reactive energy losses for electrical networks is considered. A feature of the methods of statistical analysis is their complexity, due to the variety of forms of statistical patterns, as well as the complexity of the process of statistical research. However, we want to talk about exactly such methods that everyone can use, and do it effectively and with pleasure.

Key words: overhead power lines, reactive energy losses, electrical distribution network, power transformers, reactive power factor, structural analysis.

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Power losses should be understood as energy losses over a time interval that is a multiple of a period. Distinguish between active power losses and reactive power losses. In view of objective reasons, in the future, energy losses should be understood as active energy losses. All power losses in the elements of the electric power system are usually divided into three types: The reported value of electricity losses in the power system is the difference between the amount of electricity supplied to the network (power plants, power systems, etc.) and the amount of electricity sold (the amount of paid bills from consumers) .

The calculated (technical) value of losses is determined by the known parameters of the network operation modes and the parameters of the network elements (electricity consumption for heating and creating electromagnetic fields). Commercial losses - the difference between reporting and technical losses (imperfection of the accounting system, non-simultaneity and inaccuracy of readings, instrument error, theft, etc.). Determination of electricity losses according to the load schedule (graphical integration method)

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Graph 1. The method consists in calculating the power losses at each step of the load graph and then summing these values.

This graph is a relationship between the total active power used over a certain period of time. In this case, it is considered how much energy is wasted during the period of time used power. We can see the electricity consumed directly by multiplying the power consumption by the total time. In this case, the available electricity is mainly generated in different networks. Losses of reactive energy lead to an increase in the current load of the network elements, and, consequently, an increase in active energy losses, an increased level of voltage losses in the nodes and in the network as a whole. This follows from the laws of electrical engineering.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This problem is relevant in the analysis of circuit parameters, in the choice of an appropriate equivalent circuit and optimization in the process of structural (iterative) synthesis, as well as in the synthesis of automatic control systems and

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circuits with adjustable parameters.

The following order of analysis of the circuit-mode situation is proposed:

1. In selected subsystems, according to the classes of rated voltage, the voltage deviation in the nodes is determined and its analysis is carried out for compliance with permissible parameters, nodes are identified in which a negative voltage deviation is observed, and its value is analyzed from the point of view of reactive power losses

2. In the subsystems identified by the configuration of the electrical network, an assessment is made of the influence of the electrical network scheme on the level of losses.

3. In subsystems divided according to the design of power transmission lines (TL), the influence of line resistances on the amount of losses is determined and a comparative analysis is carried out. Lines made with different sections, cable-overhead lines are distinguished. At points of common connection to networks with a voltage of 0.4.10 kV, the voltage deviation is calculated taking into account voltage losses in the network elements (lines, transformers, etc.)

When supplying electricity to consumers, it is necessary to ensure uninterrupted, reliable and high-quality electricity. But later this process is not enough. Currently, measures are being developed to facilitate the solution of this issue as much as possible. Losses of active and reactive power, as well as losses in electrical networks are taken into account during the operation of electrical networks

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Line active power loss: $\Delta P_{\text{л}} = \frac{P^2 + Q^2}{U_{\text{н}}^2} \cdot R$

Line reactive power loss: $\Delta Q_{\text{л}} = \frac{P^2 + Q^2}{U_{\text{н}}^2} \cdot X$

Loss of electricity in the line: $\Delta A_{\text{л}} = \Delta P_{\text{л}} \cdot \tau$

τ – Annual maximum operating time

III. CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the work, the following main conclusions can be drawn. Electric energy transmitted through electric networks consumes part of it for its own use. Part of the generated electricity is used to create electric and magnetic fields in electrical networks, and technological costs are necessary for its transmission, and in all directions or in each of them, as well as when identifying centers of loss. The process of calculating the consumed electricity and power is very time consuming. In the period under review, an important issue is the determination of the permissible level of losses according to economic criteria, as well as the definition of electricity, the normalization of losses. The difference between high-voltage and low-voltage capacitors is as follows: voltage 6-10 kV - up to 15%; voltage of 0.4 kV - 35 percent.

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